

Table S1: Questionnaire to promote smoking cessation for nasopharyngeal cancer prevention (English version).

Section 1: Perceptions towards nose and throat cancer

Please choose the best answer options to indicate your level of agreement.

Constructs of Health Belief Model	Questions	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Perceived susceptibility	1. I feel that I will get nose and throat cancer in the future.					
	2. My chances of getting nose and throat cancer are high.					
	3. I cannot avoid myself from getting nose and throat cancer.					
	4. I am worried about getting nose and throat cancer due to family history.					
	5. My smoking habit makes me more likely than average to get nose and throat cancer.					
Perceived seriousness	6. The thought of nose and throat cancer scares me.					
	7. If I had nose and throat cancer, the cost of treatment can be a financial strain.					
	8. Nose and throat cancer would threaten a relationship with my family.					

	9. If I had nose and throat cancer my whole life would change.					
	10. If I developed nose and throat cancer, I would not live long.					
Perceived benefits	11. Quit smoking decreases my chance of getting nose and throat cancer.					
	12. Quit smoking decreases my chance of dying from nose and throat cancer.					
	13. Quit smoking can improve my health.					
	14. I feel less anxious about nose and throat cancer if I quit smoking.					
Perceived barriers	15. It is difficult to quit tobacco smoking (e.g., peer pressure).					
	16. I feel anxious without smoking.					
	17. Tobacco smoking relieves my stress.					
	18. I experience headache without smoking.					
	19. I experience excessive salivation without smoking.					
	20. I think getting nose and throat cancer is destiny and quitting smoking will not change it.					
Cues to action	21. I will quit smoking if I have social support.					

	22. I will quit smoking if there are information sources that reminds me. (Examples of sources include: the internet, newspapers, radio and TV).					
	23. I will quit smoking if I have the will to change.					
	24. I will quit smoking if I know the diseases related to smoking.					
	25. I will quit smoking if there are health professionals to assist me.					
Self-efficacy	26. I can refuse to smoke when I am thinking about difficult problem.					
	27. I can refuse the urge to smoke.					
	28. I can refuse to smoke when I see someone else smoking.					
	29. I can refuse to smoke when offered by my friends/ family.					
	30. I can refuse from buying cigarettes when I have extra pocket money.					

Section 2: Health Behavioural Intention on smoking cessation

Please choose the best answer options to indicate your level of agreement.

Statements	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
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1. I would like to lead a healthier lifestyle to prevent nose and throat cancer.					
2. I am trying to quit smoking to prevent nose and throat cancer at this time.					
3. I plan to quit smoking to prevent nose and throat cancer within six months.					
4. I would like to quit smoking to prevent nose and throat cancer but have never really tried.					